

Table S1.

	Age (years)	Body weight (g)	Body height (cm)	BMI (%)	Body fat (%)	Waist perimeter (cm)	Hip perimeter (cm)
Women with normal-weight	21.9 ± 1.0	58.4 ± 2.7	167 ± 2	21.0 ± 0.7	31.8 ± 1.0	68.1 ± 1.8	96.3 ± 1.8
Men with normal-weight	22.5 ± 1.6	73.3 ± 4.1	180 ± 4	22.5 ± 0.7	17.9 ± 2.3	80.3 ± 3.4	100 ± 3
Women with overweight or obesity	23.8 ± 2.3	77.9 ± 4.7	159 ± 3	31.1 ± 2.2	40.6 ± 2.4	83.0 ± 4.8	113 ± 5